

EFFECT OF SUITABLE STORAGE CONTAINER ON SEED GERMINATION OF *Melia azedarach* and *Azadirachta indica* OF MELIACEAE

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Abstract:

The present study was carried out to study the "Effect of suitable storage container on seed germination of important forest tree species *Melia azedarach* and *Azadirachta indica* of Meliaceae family" was conducted during the year 2021-22 for the period of four months. The study was conducted at premises of Department of forestry of Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth Akola. Study was conducted to identify the suitable storage container among Cotton bag (T1), Gunny bag (T2), Poly bag (T3) and Tin container (T4), which used as a treatment for the seeds of important forest tree species of Meliaceae family, *Melia azedarach* (S1) and *Azadirachta indica* (S2) for better Germination. Among the selected storage containers, the Tin container (T4) was found to be most superior for moisture content as well as germination percent, and found to be most ideal one for prolonging seed viability and seed storage.

Keywords: *Melia azedarach*, *Azadirachta indica*, Storage containers, Germination

Introduction

Storage of native forest tree seeds is essential for the development of seed-based forest restoration methods, such as direct or aerial seeding and for increasing representation of native trees in nurseries, for conventional tree planting (Waiboonya *et al.* 2019). When the seed season arrives, it is very important to maintain seed viability. As seeds age increases their germination rate naturally declines. Storage of seeds in proper condition can allow many seeds to remain viable even longer.

Bakan (*Melia azedarach*) and Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) are tow economically important tree species in Vidarbha region belongs to the family *Meliaceae*. These are the most valuable multipurpose tree species for rural and urban people of India. *Melia azedarach* is moderate deciduous trees with a short bole and a spreading crown, bipinnate or tri-pinnate leaves and a dark grey bark (Troup 1921). Both the species are popular for dense, dark green foliage in summer and both trees an attractive fast-growing thrives in a variety of soils, and the species are cold-hardy and drought-resistant. Plantations of these trees improve the environmental condition of the country and helps to reduce soil erosion. Different parts like bark, leaf, seeds, root of *Melia azedarach* and *Azadirachta indica* have very strong medicinal value and the seeds of these species can also be used as biological control of fungicide and pesticide of agricultural crops. Almost all parts of the trees have one or several uses. Multipurpose trees in the real sense.

Azadirachta indica tree has long been used in medicine and provides basic needs in the rural households in terms of pesticides, mosquito repellent, fertilizers, diabetic food, soaps, lubricants, gums, agricultural implements, tooth paste, tooth brush sticks and even contraceptives. Neem oil is used against stomach ulcer, worm infection and rheumatism. The wood of *Melia azedarach* species is very hard and durable. Therefore, timber of this species is very important for furniture industry and it can also meet the demand of

fuel wood. Hence, it can be introduced in all over the country. Therefore, it is mandatory to preserve the seeds of both species for future. Maintaining seed viability for longer period is very essential to preserve the genetic integrity in stored samples.

Material and Methods

As per the availability of the seeds during stipulated time the well mature seeds of *Melia azedarach* and *Azadirachta indica*, were randomly collected from Akola District including Dr. P.D.K.V. Akola main campus, and recorded the fresh weight of the seeds. freshly harvested seeds of selected species were cleaned and graded. Then seeds were air-dried to bring the moisture content at required level and recorded the dry weight of seeds. Through fresh weight and dry weight pre storage moisture content was noted using following formula:

$$\text{Moisture Content} = \frac{\text{Fresh Weight} - \text{Dry Weight}}{\text{Fresh Weight}} \times 100$$

Thereafter, pre storage germination (%) was recorded then seeds were kept in different selected containers viz. cotton bag, gunny bag, poly bag and tin container and placed at ambient temperature in the laboratory of Department of Forestry, Dr. P.D.K.V Akola. Storage was done for four months. Germination percentage was recorded after every one-month interval up to four months. The three replications of 50 seeds from different storage treatment were sown in line in polybags and germination tray in ambient atmosphere. The seeds were counted as germinated when cotyledons emergence from soil. The germination testing period was 28 days. After every 28 days seed sowing, germination (%) was counted by the following formula:

$$\text{Germination \%} = \frac{\text{Number of seeds germinated}}{\text{Total number of seeds sown}} \times 100$$

The experiment comprises of four treatments such as T1 (Cotton bag), T2 (Gunny bag), T3 (Poly bag) and T4 (Tin container) and two species combination like S1 (Karanj) and S2 (Siris). The experimental details are as follows given in Table 1.

Table 1. Treatments details and their description

Sr. no.	Treatment	Treatment description
1	T1S1	Cotton bag + Bakan
2	T1S2	Cotton bag + Neem
3	T2S1	Gunny bag + Bakan
4	T2S2	Gunny bag + Neem
5	T3S1	Poly bag + Bakan
6	T3S2	Poly bag + Neem
7	T4S1	Tin container + Bakan
8	T4S2	Tin container + Neem

Results and Discussion

The results of the present investigation based on the various observations viz., fresh weight of seeds (g), pre storage moisture

content of seeds (%), pre storage germination of seeds (%), post-storage moisture content of seeds at one month interval up to four months, post-storage germination percentage of stored seeds at one month interval (%) up to four months are presented and discussed here. All the observation were taken in ambient condition and the data was analysed in appropriate statistical design.

The data presented in Table 2; Fig. 1 showed that the maximum pre storage moisture content was recorded after collection of seeds in treatment T4S1 (Tin container + Karanj), 17.07 % followed by T3S1 (Poly bag + Karanj) 17.03 %. Further, the data indicates that with increasing in storage period the moisture content of both the species was gradually decreases with respect to different containers. The maximum moisture content was recorded in T4S1 (Tin container + Karanj) 16.20 % followed by T3S1 (Poly bag + Karanj) 16.02 %. Tin container recorded highest moisture content compared to other container this variation observed might be due to air tight nature of tin container. Similar results were recorded by Ali *et al.* (2014) and Naznin *et al.* (2005).

The data presented in Table 3; Fig. 2 showed that the maximum pre storage germination was recorded when seeds were sown after collection in treatment T4S2 (Tin container + Neem), 77.00 %. Data also revealed that with the increase in storage period the germination percent decreased in different treatments. However, in treatment T4 the germination % was retain higher in all the selected specie after

120 days (four month), the maximum germination was recorded 85.00 % in T4S1 (Tin container + Bakan) treatment. Followed by 84.00 % in T4S2 (Tin container + Neem). However, the minimum germination percent was recorded 73.00 % in T1S2 (Gunny bag + Neem) and T3S2 (Poly bag + Neem) after fourth month. The better performance of treatment T4 (Tin container) may be due to preservation of moisture content which leads to better germinability over its counterparts. Similar results were recorded by Khalequzzaman *et al.* (2012), Nabila *et al.* (2016) and Akter *et al.* (2014) respectively. However, all these studies conducted for the agriculture crops. For long term seed storage, we have required most appropriate container and temperature. Temperature substratum play a very significant role during the process of seed germination. Seed of some species germinate better at constant temperature while other alternate temperature (Kumar and Gopal 1974). Storage may be defined as the preservation of viable seeds from the time of collection until they are required for sowing. General knowledge of good storage methods is of great economic importance on properly applied, it can be ensuring the availability of seed for regular and early distribution and enable seed stocks to be built up in good seed year. (Holmes and Buszewicz, 1958). Container form an integral part of storage facilities, container provide insulation against moisture and prevent the seed form equilibrating with the ambient relative humidity (Willan, 1985, Lavania and Tiwari 2019).

Table 2. Effect of storage containers on moisture content of seeds with increasing storage periods

Treatment	Pre storage moisture content (%)	1 st month moisture content (%)	2 nd month moisture content (%)	3 rd month moisture content (%)	4 th month moisture content (%)
T1S1	16.96 (4.23)	16.22 (4.15)	15.86 (4.10)	15.50 (4.06)	15.17 (4.02)
T1S2	16.77 (4.21)	16.18 (4.14)	15.88 (4.10)	15.54 (4.06)	15.20 (4.02)
T2S1	16.82 (4.22)	16.14 (4.14)	15.72 (4.08)	15.48 (4.06)	15.22 (4.02)
T2S2	16.68 (4.20)	16.08 (4.13)	15.80 (4.09)	15.58 (4.07)	15.25 (4.03)
T3S1	17.03 (4.24)	16.70 (4.20)	16.34 (4.16)	16.20 (4.14)	16.02 (4.12)
T3S2	16.72 (4.21)	16.30 (4.15)	16.18 (4.14)	16.02 (4.12)	15.89 (4.11)
T4S1	17.07 (4.25)	16.76 (4.21)	16.52 (4.18)	16.33 (4.16)	16.20 (4.14)
T4S2	16.71 (4.20)	16.46 (4.17)	16.24 (4.15)	16.06 (4.13)	15.91 (4.11)

The value in parenthesis indicates square root transformation value.

Table 3. Effect of storage containers on germination percentage of seeds with increasing storage periods

Treatment	Pre storage germination Percent (%)	1 st month germination Percent (%)	2 nd month germination Percent (%)	3 rd month germination Percent (%)	4 th month germination Percent (%)
T1S1	72.00 (8.54)	83.00 (9.16)	81.00 (9.05)	78.00 (8.00)	76.00 (8.77)
T1S2	75.00 (8.71)	83.00 (9.16)	78.00 (8.88)	77.00 (8.83)	73.00 (8.60)
T2S1	74.00 (8.66)	82.00 (9.11)	80.00 (9.00)	76.00 (8.77)	74.00 (8.66)
T2S2	76.00 (8.77)	82.00 (9.11)	79.00 (8.94)	74.00 (8.66)	74.00 (8.66)
T3S1	73.00 (8.60)	84.00 (9.21)	79.00 (8.94)	76.00 (8.77)	76.00 (8.77)
T3S2	75.00 (8.71)	81.00 (9.05)	78.00 (8.88)	76.00 (8.77)	73.00 (8.60)
T4S1	75.00 (8.71)	88.00 (9.43)	87.00 (9.38)	86.00 (9.32)	85.00 (9.27)
T4S2	77.00 (8.83)	87.00 (9.38)	85.00 (9.27)	85.00 (9.27)	84.00 (9.21)

The value in parenthesis indicates square root transformation value.

Fig. 1 Effect of storage containers on moisture content of seeds with increasing storage periods

Fig. 2 Effect of storage containers on germination percentage of seeds with increasing storage periods

Conclusion

In the light of the results obtained from these investigations, following conclusions are arrived. With increase in seed storage period a gradual decrease in germination per cent of seeds of all the species was observed. The seed stored in tin container (T4) in ambient condition excelled all other storage containers by maintaining highest germination percent for all the selected important forest tree species. However, minimum loss of germination percent was recorded when seeds were stored in tin container (T4)

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